

Utilization of Deep Reinforcement Learning for Swarm Systems

By

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*In the Name of ALLAH, Most Gracious,
Most Merciful*

*Dedicated to my Parents, Teachers, and Friends for their love,
affection, and support.*

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Nomenclature

UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle
PSO	Particle Swarm Optimization
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
DDPG	Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient
PPO	Proximal Policy Optimization

Abstract

The presence of swarm intelligence in many natural systems has always been an inspiration to develop such distributed intelligence in artificial multi-agent systems. It finds its applications in high-level control of complex swarms, distributed sensing technologies, and telecom networks. For quite some time, many researchers are trying to manually develop artificial swarm models with more and more capabilities, but manual modeling is tedious and becomes impractical as the complexity of the problem grows manifolds. However, due to recent advancements in computational devices, many end-to-end solutions are being considered, lowering the gap between the artificial and the natural swarms. In this research, we present an end-to-end approach to train a group of cooperative agents to navigate through 3-dimensional (3D) environments. The problem is particularly hard because the agents can only observe the environment partially and the number of agents in the swarm (also known as the size of the swarm) may change over time. Our approach uses deep reinforcement learning, mapping raw sensory data to high-level commands, to optimize (1) navigation, and (2) distributed assembly of the swarm while keeping the swarm (3) unaffected from its size dynamics. Here, we use suitable reward shaping for navigation and distributed assembly and deal size dynamics by exploiting histograms as an observational input to the model. The simulations were performed in the Unity 3D engine. During the research, focused sets of neural network parameters, environment complexities, observation vectors, action types, and reward functions were developed and applied. The results demonstrate that our approach effectively improves swarm navigation and assembly in 3D environments and can be generalized to real-world scenarios.

Chapter 1 : Introduction

Nature has systems in which actions of many decentralized and self-organized simple agents give rise to “intelligent” global behavior, called “swarm intelligence”. Examples include a colony of ants, fish school, birds flock, etc. These swarm systems use the “number” and the “coordination” as the tools to achieve common goals such as foraging, collective manipulation, and formation control.

The field of swarm robotics studies these biological swarm systems and infer the underlying phenomena to devise models that drive artificial swarm systems. Every swarm which occurs in nature has quite a big set of behaviors combined seamlessly, for example, a prey retrieval task in an ant colony requires both navigation and formation at the same time. However, in most cases of artificial swarm systems, such a combination of behaviors is hard to model as modeling a combination of behaviors adds complexity to the problem. It is even harder when such modeling is manual.

In this research, we present an end-to-end deep reinforcement learning solution to solve a complex swarm navigation problem. The problem consists of three clauses which ensure safe navigation towards a destination point while keeping the swarm organized, the clauses are 1) the swarm needs to navigate towards a destination point in a 3D space, 2) agents of the swarm should stay in a communication radius to each other but should maintain a safe distance to avoid any inter-agent collisions, and 3) agents must avoid any obstacles throughout the journey.

Each agent is equipped with sensors to measure distances to nearby obstacles, a communication device which can transmit and receive position data to and from nearby agents, and a positioning system module. Using the obstacle sensors input, position data of nearby agents, and awareness of its position each agent must decide its next position in the 3D space while adhering to the aforementioned clauses. The problem is particularly interesting because each agent can only observe in a limited radius and the number of agents that are in that radius may change. In the context of neural networks, such variations are hard to tackle because of their fixed-size nature. Here, we formulate a suitable reward function that incorporates all the subtle requirements of the problem as described by the clauses. Moreover, a 3D histogram representation is proposed to cope with the variations in the number of neighboring agents to any given individual.

1.1 Purpose of Project

The purpose of this research project is to explore state-of-art deep reinforcement learning methodologies to model three important swarm behaviors, (1) navigation towards a destination point, (2) maintaining formation, and (3) avoid any obstacles throughout the journey inside a 3D environment.

1.2 Scope of Research

This research is using Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL). The DRL combines techniques from, both, reinforcement learning and the Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) to create end-to-end solutions. The research is particularly focused on finding practical solutions to the aforementioned problem by training (in simulation) the agents inside a 3D environment that resembles real-world scenarios.

1.3 Report Organization

The 2nd chapter describes the literature review. The problem design and experimentation details are given in the 3rd chapter, starting from basic investigations to implementations of many state-of-art deep reinforcement learning models. Chapter 4 provides technical details of the experimentation. Finally, an end-note and references are given in chapters 5 and 6 respectively.

Chapter 2 : Literature Review

In this chapter, a detailed review of the available literature is given which is not only the inspiration for this research but provides insights on how reinforcement learning emerged to be one of the most researched areas in artificial intelligence (AI).

The robot swarms are inspired by biological swarm systems. Since the biological swarm systems often exceed, in performance, when compared with the capabilities of individual biological creatures, the researchers have always been interested in extracting and applying the rules which govern those amazing swarm systems. In the past, great accomplishments were made incorporating manual inspection and emulation of swarms. Kube et al. [1] studied rules governing large prey retrieval in ants and used these extracted rules to describe an implementation of this phenomenon in robots. Nouyan et al. [2] also studied robot swarms of up to 12 agents performing foraging tasks. Minaeian et al. [3] handcrafted motion detection and localization algorithms in a group of unmanned ground vehicles (UGVs) and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) to track and control crowds. Antonio et al. [4] studied pheromone-based localization of distributed targets in a swarm of virtual agents working in a simulated discretized environment. In their work the mini-UAVs are considered as the agents of swarm and agents may have imperfections when sensing. In a work by Bahareh et al. [5] the use of particle swarm optimization (PSO) is enhanced using A* (local method of search) to escape local minima which is a common problem seen in PSO based swarms. Bandala et al. studied swarm behavior like aggregation, foraging, formation and tracking, and gave algorithms to emulate those behaviors. However, the human capacity to solve problems faces limitations when the complexity of the problem grows manifolds. So, there's need to lower the manual inspection, formulation and solution of any given problem.

Q-Learning, a way to iteratively train agents to act optimally to get the maximum reward, was introduced in 1992 by Watkins et al. [6]. It was proved with a probability of 1 that Q-Learning converges to give optimum action-value pairs in Markovian domains if given enough samples data. In 2013, Volodymyr et al. [7] at Google Deep Mind developed the first deep learning model based on Q-Learning. It successfully learned playing many Atari 2600 games from pixels input. Q-Learning is a continuous state but discrete action space algorithm, to tackle this problem Lillicrap et. al. [8] gave an actor-

critic based algorithm, called deep deterministic policy gradient, which follows a lot from DQN to for its basic design along with mini-batch updates and Ornstein-Uhlenbeck Process as noise for exploration.

Maximilian et. al. [9]-[10] studied swarm assembly and cooperative localization. They used DDPG algorithm with slight modifications. They changed the actor network and critic network input to make it work on the swarm system. In their new approach, they presented complete state to critic network only while the actor network could only observe partial state data. This forces the critic network to update the actor network parameters based on global state data while actor network uses only local state information.

In an approach given by Akhloufi et al. [11], a deep learning model is used to predict the actions of the agents following a moving drone. Wang et al. [12] used deep reinforcement learning to train a single agent to navigate in a complex maze-like environment. In their study data from locality sensors and a GPS device was used as an observational input to a memory enabled deep network. A similar work by Yan et al. [13] is also there.

The simulations are not easy to model, [14] introduces the unity game/physics engine and supported the ml-agents library for easy implementation of custom simulations for almost every kind of problem. The ml-agents library provides a very good interface between the engine and the python programming language. It provides easy methods for state observations, taking actions, rewards implementation, and engine-to-python communication. [15] describes OpenAI Gym library which uses MuJoCo [16] physics engine and has many environments to benchmark reinforcement learning algorithms.

The “Proximal Policy Optimization Algorithms” [17] is a recent paper from Google Deep Mind. It became a state-of-the-art algorithm to train agents because of its sample efficiency. It optimizes a “surrogate” clipped objective function using a stochastic gradient ascent. The PPO algorithm performed better than A2C [18] and ACER [19] on the Atari domain. The problems like humanoid running and steering in OpenAI Gym were also tested using PPO algorithms to show its performance on high-dimensional controls. Distributed Proximal Policy Optimization (DPPO) [20] is used to train multiple agents achieving optimizing one global reward.

Chapter 3 : Problem Design and Experimentation

During this study, we started with basic capability testing of Deep Deterministic Policy Gradients and Proximal Policy Optimization algorithms by testing these on some benchmark problems provided in various libraries, then we gradually modified algorithms and techniques to focus more and more on our particular problem. We simulated many types of agents, in both 2D and 3D environments with a lot of different rewards settings. The custom simulations were created inside the Unity Engine. Unity provides many tools to develop physical simulations of the world and provide a very good machine learning interface to interact with other machine learning libraries and frameworks.

The following are the details of the workflow we followed.

3.1 Investigating Deep Q-Learning (DQN) algorithm

The DQN [7] algorithm showed promising results on Atari 2600 games, it outperformed all previous approaches and even surpassed human expert on three of the games. On investigation, we found that Atari 2600 games are discrete action space problems, that is, the games require discrete values as actions. The DQN algorithm is a continuous space and discrete action space algorithm which can't be used in our case, where the required output is continuous.

3.2 Implementation of Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) algorithm

In order to tackle the discrete action space limitation of the DQN algorithm, we implemented an algorithm given by Lillicrap *et. al.* [8], this algorithm takes continuous state values as input and outputs continuous action values. In order to validate the implementation and convergence of this algorithm, we used the *Lunar Lander V2* environment from OpenAI Gym [15]. It is a single agent, fixed environment problem with continuous state and action space. The agent which spawns at top of the screen in random orientation and velocity must land safely to get a positive reward. DDPG algorithm was able to successfully learn the policy. Figure 1 shows the environment visuals.

Figure 1: DDPG Algorithm Validity Test
Lunar Lander V2 Environment, Open AI Gym

3.3 Modification of DDPG Implementation to Deal with Partial Observability

One agent problems with full observability like *Lunar Lander V2* are easy to work because the agent knows its global state, i.e. all the information needed to optimize the reward is provided. In our swarm intelligence problem, we must tackle partial observability i.e. the agent knows very limited information about the environment and itself. Maximilian *et. al.* [10] successfully trained swarm agents with the same goals as ours but in a small 2D space. In their model they obtained both local and global observation data during training, they then allowed the policy network to see only local observation data and presented the global state data only to the critic network. The intuition behind this was that the critic network is only used during the training phase and presenting global state data to this network doesn't break the rule of partial observability. The critic network is like a coach seeing the whole field and training players with partial observability to act coordinatively. This approach was surprisingly successful at training agents according to their publication.

This approach took our attention because it managed to solve a problem quite similar to ours, so we thought maybe scaling the networks along with some parameter tuning can improve training in our 3D space problem, so we tested with 3, 5, and 8 agents in a 10x10x10 environment comprising of space only (i.e. there were no obstacles in the environment). The most promising behavior was seen in 5 agents' scenario. The agents randomly moved and upon finding the target point, kept themselves close to it. But as the target point was too sparse given the area of the environment and very limited sensing capabilities of agents, the swarm failed to converge after a few seconds, and the agents disperse randomly to voids of space. Due to limited computational resources and given sample inefficiency of DDPG algorithm, we couldn't perform the experiments on large-scale training data. Figure 2 shows the environment visuals.

Figure 2: DDPG: Simple Simulation

The observability is partial. The rewards are based on organization and localization.

In the figure, we can see the group of 3 agents has formed formation (the green edge between any two agents shows that both agents are in safe formation, i.e. not colliding but are in the communication).

3.4 Implementation of Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm

The Proximal Policy Optimization algorithm [17] is marked as current state-of-art in deep reinforcement learning because it was able to beat human champions at Dota 2 (an advanced level online battle game) and most importantly it is very sample efficient as compared to DDPG. It was implemented and to test it, we designed a custom environment in which quadcopters agents had to keep flying to get the positive reward. The PPO algorithm was able to learn this behavior and showed good performance in sample efficiency.

Figure 3: Basic Quadcopter Drone Agent

3.5 Implementation of Big-Scale Environment and Experimentation using PPO algorithm

Since the implementation was fine, we moved and developed a big-scale environment to test the performance of PPO algorithm on some fresh and intuitive observation vectors, action types, and reward functions. The big-scale environment was 100x100x20 units, in which 25 buildings were generated with random widths (of up to 5 units) and heights (of up to 20 units) at random positions, each episode. 12 drones of size 1x1x0.2 units were deployed at a random position in each episode. Each agent had 26 time-of-flight sensors covering a radius of 5 units around the agent. The sensors could detect both obstacles and the target. Each agent was also equipped with a communication device that could be used to broadcast position data of target, if found and an accurate 3D positioning device that told the agent its X, Y, and Z position in the area. Target was spawned at a random position in each episode (it usually fell on the ground but sometimes it fell on building tops increasing the complexity of the problem). Figure 4 and Figure 5 show the visuals of the environment with one agent.

Figure 4: The Big-Scale Environment

The colored blocks of various sizes are obstacles and black spheres with black spikes are agents. The position target is shown with a vertical black line going all the way up, the target is at the bottom of that line.

Figure 5: Single Drone Agent in Action

We conducted 4 experiments on this environment, ranging from 10 to 50 million step-frame training data (this much data is low-minimum of what is necessary to train agents in this complex environment). Some good behavior learnings were achieved where agents successfully learned to fly smoothly and avoided collisions (with the buildings and each other). The agents even manage to find the target sometimes and gathered like birds flock around it. But it is still not mature enough to avoid collision totally or find good patterns to search the target (sometimes rapid collisions are seen once the target is found). The reasons behind these failures could be too much sparsity of the target, ineffective reward modeling, or simply the complexity of the environment in which agents are spawned. These reasons are being considered one at a time and possible intuitive solutions are being tested.

3.6 Improvements in Big-Scale Environment and Swarm Model Improvements

The simulation design for the swarm navigation problem is crucial because it directly affects the quality of training data that the agents will encounter, so we improved the environment, by extending the obstacle placement in all the 3-axis rather than on an x-plane. The other modifications are as follows: a 3D space covering a cubical volume of 1,000,000 units³, the length of each axis being 100 units, is assigned as the environment volume per simulation where 100 random sized obstacles ranging from 1 to 10 units of length, width, and height spawn at random positions (Figure 6-a).

To place a destination point in the environment, a random tick approach is used; at each time-step, a random floating number, ranging from 0 to 1, is generated; if the number generated is greater than or equal to 0.9 the time-step is considered to be a tick. The position of the destination point in the environment is randomized every 120 ticks. The random tick approach introduces time-decoupled randomness to the position of the destination point.

The agents spawn at random positions in the environment. Each agent can sense obstacles using the distance sensors arranged in a spherical pattern around the agent's body (Figure 6-a). If the agents get closer than a certain communication radius, they can communicate their absolute positions to each other (Figure 6-b).

Figure 6: Improved Big-Scale Environment

The outer gray box outlines the boundary of the environment in sub-figure (a); randomly placed agents (bodies with yellow spikes) are also shown. In sub-figure (b) the communication-enabled region of an agent (depicted by the transparent white circle) and sensor rays (depicted by yellow lines) are shown.

3.6.1 Modeling State

Each agent observes a state vector containing information about the destination point and its neighborhood. It is assumed that the destination point is always known at each time-step. To have a compact representation of the destination point, we propose a normalized relative direction vector representation and a sigmoid of the distance between the destination point and the agent. For simplicity purposes, the coordinate systems of both the agents and the destination point are aligned before running the simulations. The rotation properties of the agents are then locked to prevent any coordinate system misalignments. The normalized relative direction vector s (Eq. 01) and sigmoid of distance (Eq. 02) between destination point P_y and agent P_i can then be computed as follows:

$$\mathbf{s} = \frac{P_y - P_i}{\|P_y - P_i\|} \quad (\text{Eq. 01})$$

$$\sigma_{d_i^y} = \frac{\|P_y - P_i\|}{1 + \|P_y - P_i\|} \quad (\text{Eq. 02})$$

where P_y and P_i represent the destination point y and the position of the agent i respectively.

The neighborhood information in the state vector includes positional data of other agents that are inside the communication region and values from obstacle sensors. Since the number of agents in the neighborhood may change irregularly and deep neural networks have a static input size, it is hard to input position data of neighboring agents directly to the network. To tackle this issue, we propose a 3D histogram approach that works by mapping vector components of position difference vectors between agent i

and the neighboring agents into K bins per axis. The proposed method is to concatenate histograms for all three axes into one linear vector. The linear vector can then be presented to the neural network.

The algorithm to compute the histogram for vector component $\langle c \rangle$ for agent i (Algo. 1) is as follows:

Algo. 1: Histogram Over Vector Components

Initialize:

$$hist_k^{\langle c \rangle} \leftarrow 0, k = 1, 2 \dots K$$

for $m = 1$ to M do

$$k = \left\lceil \frac{\langle c \rangle_i^m + D_{com}}{D_{com} \times 2} \times K - 1 \right\rceil, c \in \{x, y, z\}$$

$$hist_k^{\langle c \rangle} += \begin{cases} \frac{1 - \sigma d_i^m}{M \times 3}, & \text{if } D_{safe} \leq d_i^m \leq D_{com} \\ -1, & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

where M is the number of the agents in the swarm excluding agent i , $\langle c \rangle_i^m$ denotes the difference in c component of position vectors of agent m and i , d_i^m is the distance between agent m and i ; D_{safe} and D_{com} are the parameters for safe distance and communication radius respectively.

The obstacle sensors of the agents are assumed to be time-of-flight sensors for obstacle sensing in a limited range D_{sensor} . Each sensor j returns a value v_j (Eq. 03) which is modeled as follows:

$$v_j = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{d_j}{D_{sensor}}, & \text{if } j \text{ senses an obstacle} \\ 0, & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (\text{Eq. 03})$$

where d_j is the raw distance value returned by sensor j . The values of all the J sensors are then concatenated and presented to the neural network.

Figure 7: Modeling State

3.6.2 Modeling Action

To generalize the use of our approach, we output a delta vector V consisting of three continuous values. The delta vector V is then added to the agent's current position vector P_i to formulate the next position P_i' (Eq. 04).

$$\hat{P}_i = P_i + V \quad (\text{Eq. 04})$$

$$P_i' = P_i + V \quad \text{where } V \in \mathbb{R}^3 \text{ and } V = [0,1]$$

Figure 8: Modeling Action

Chapter 4 : Technical Details

During this research, we tried sets of observation vectors, action types, reward functions, and environments, this section provides details and intuitions behind all these parameters of experiments. Since we are also giving details of the past experiments with unsatisfactory results, the last row (highlighted with a bold style number) of each of these tables tells the finalized case where the results were best.

Note: Only the parameters that directly play role in the research are presented here. The parameters used in the pre-testing of algorithms to investigate their convergence, sample efficiency, etc. (like the use of PPO algorithm for training quadcopter drones to optimize their flight time) are omitted for simplicity purposes.

4.1 Observation Vectors

#	Observation Vector	Description/Intuition
1	Histogram Over Distances + Distance to Target Used in a small-scale environment.	Due to partial observability, the number of agents in the detection radius may increase or decrease over time, but neural networks input is always of fixed size, so histogram over distances was used as a distance observation vector. If the target is in the detection radius of the agent, the distance to the target is also included in observations. A value of -1 is passed otherwise. This tells the agent to stay in the vicinity of the target, once found.

2	<p>Observation Vector # 1 + Moving Local Memory</p> <p>Used in a small-scale environment.</p>	<p>It was developed by the researcher and added to observation vector # 1. The intuition behind this was to enable agents to recall recent actions to optimize their next action.</p>
3	<p>Observation Vector # 2 + Relative Position</p> <p>Used in a small-scale environment.</p>	<p>It is mathematically easy to compute the relative position of the agent (relative to its starting position). It may add a cognitive understanding in agents to optimize their search strategy.</p>
4	<p>Observation Vector # 2 + Absolute Position</p> <p>Used in a small-scale environment.</p>	<p>This was just added to test how quickly an agent reaches in the vicinity of the target if the target is found by some other agent and the exact location of the target is broadcasted.</p>
5	<p>Observation Vector # 3,4 + Absolute Rotation</p> <p>Used in a small-scale environment.</p>	<p>The agents move using 4 continuous values, the first 3 values tell the direction vector and 4th value tells the scale of that vector. Allowing agents to know their rotation (direction vector) in 3D space could generate better decisions.</p>
6	<p>Sensors Data + Target Found Bool + Target Location</p> <p>Used in a big-scale environment.</p>	<p>A vector of 26 sensor data was tested when experimenting in big-scale environments, each sensor data was a 3 valued vector itself, containing, a bool to tell if something hit the sensor, an int id for the identity of the hit, and float value for distance to hit.</p>

7	Observation Vector # 6 + Swarm's Mean Position + Swarm's Standard Deviation Used in a big-scale environment.	Swarm's Mean Position and Standard Deviation was added to tell the agent where the search is intense, so the agents can decide optimally where it should search.
8	Normalized Direction to Destination Point + Normalized Distance to Destination Point + Histogram Over Vector Components to Neighbours + Normalized Values of Obstacle Distance Sensors	This factor ingeniously blends all the information required to achieve localization, formation, and obstacle avoidance. It was finalized to be the best observation vector.

Table 1: Observation Vector Experimentations

4.2 Action Types

#	Action	Description/Intuition
1	X, Y, Z Rotation + Scale Used in a small-scale environment.	Rotation (X, Y, Z) * Scale, tells the next position where the agents should move. X, Y, Z, and Scale are all continuous.
2	X, Y, Z Rotation Only Used in the big-scale environment	The scale was removed and instead a gradually increasing speed limited by max value is applied in big-scale environment agents, this adds smoothness in their movement.
3	Deltas of X, Y, Z only	This is the action type that proved successful. In this only delta values of all the axis are added to our position vector. The max length of the vector is 0.5 units.

Table 2: Action Experimentations

4.3 Reward Functions

#	Reward Functions	Description/Intuition
1	$R(s, a) = \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{m>1}^M 1_{[1.5,3]}(d_m^i) - 0.05 \sum_{i=1}^M \ a^i\ _2$	<p>This is an organization reward given in [9]. The agents are rewarded based on the number of pairwise distances between 1.5 and 3. The distance between 1.5 and 3 is considered to be the safe distance, the agents must maintain. It allows agents to stay close (organization) and prevent inter collisions. M is the total number of agents. d_m^i is the distance between agent i and m. $\ a^i\$ is magnitude of action. It is designed to count unique edges.</p>
2	$R(s, a) = \sum_{i=1}^M l_i - 0.05 \sum_{i=1}^M \ a^i\ _2$	<p>The agents are provided with the observation $o^i = [l^i, d_T^i, u^i]$ where l^i is the localization bit, d_T^i is the distance to the target if it is within the communication radius (-1 if it is not), and u^i is the distribution over distances to agents within the communication range.</p>

3	$R(s, a) = -0.01 \sum_{i=1}^M 1 - 1_{[-5,5]} d_C^i$	<p>This reward was developed for a small-scale environment with 3, 5, and 8 agent scenarios. It gives a penalty of -0.01 to every agent which is outside the fixed area. M is the total number of agents. $1_{[-5,5]} d_C^i$ is equal to 1 if the distance between i^{th} agent and center C lies between -5 and 5 units in all X, Y, and Z-axis. It is 0 otherwise.</p>
4	$R(s, a) = -1 \sum_{i=1}^M 1 - 1_{[-50,50]_{x,z}, [0,20]_y} d_C^i$	<p>This is the same reward as reward # 3 except it is designed for a big-scale environment with X and Z axis limits of -50 to 50 and Y-axis limit of 0 to 20 units, also, it put even greater force to train the agents inside the arena by giving a bigger penalty on leaving the arena and ending the episode for no more positive rewards in that episode.</p>

5	$R(s, a) = -1 \sum_{i=1}^M H_i \times O_i \times 1_{(-\infty, 0.2]} d_H^i$	<p>This is a crash penalty. Whenever an agent detects an obstacle and the distance to the obstacle is less than 0.2 units, he receives a -1 reward. H_i is 1 if any of 26 sensors detect something, otherwise it is 0. O_i denotes detected object identity which is 1 for obstacle and 0 for target and $1_{(-\infty, 0.2]} d_H^i$ is 1 if the distance between agent i and detected object H is less than or equal to 0.2 units.</p>
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$$R(s, a) = -0.001 \sum_{i=1}^M H_i \times O_i \times \frac{1_{[0.2, L]} d_H^i}{d_H^i}$$

The above reward forces agents to jump out of place if an obstacle is detected. That limits the agents to only work in very open areas. Since an agent may spawn in an area where there are many obstacles, it must learn that if there is an obstacle near, it is alright, just don't get too close to it. This reward is the same as reward # 5 but the last term is changed from $1_{[-\infty, 0.2]} d_H^i$ to $(1_{[0.2, L]} d_H^i / d_H^i)$. This changes the behavior from a big negative penalty to a low penalty which gradually increases as the agent move close to the obstacle. This allows the agents to avoid obstacles but not in a haphazard way.

7	$R(s, a) = \sum_{i=1}^M l \times \frac{1}{d_T^i}$	<p>This reward forces the agent to move close to target once the target is located by any other agent. l_i is a global variable, whenever any agent detects target in its vicinity, it broadcast the location of the target T and set l to 1. d_T^i is the distance between agent i and target T.</p>
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8	$R_{nav} = \begin{cases} 1 - \sigma(d_i^y - D_{safe}), & \text{if } d_i^y \in [D_{safe}, \infty) \\ -1, & \text{else} \end{cases}$ $R_{org} = \sum_{m=1}^M \begin{cases} \frac{1 - \sigma d_i^m}{M \times 3}, & \text{if } d_i^m \in [D_{safe}, D_{communication}] \\ -1, & \text{else} \end{cases}$ $R_{safe} = 1 - \sigma(\sum_{j=1}^J v_j)$ $R_{swarm} = R_{nav} + R_{org} + R_{safe}$	<p>The reward R_{swarm} is the final reward function used in our PPO experiment and was proved to be successful at modeling the required behavior. Here, R_{nav} minimizes the distance to the destination point, R_{org} is responsible for organizing agents so that they stay in communication with each other and R_{safe} is the obstacle avoidance reward. Any agent leaving the environment gets a negative 5 reward and its position is randomized.</p>
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Table 3: Reward Function Developments

4.4 Environments

#	Environments	Description/Intuition
1	Small-Scale Environment	This environment is a 10x10x10 box-shaped environment. It comprises space everywhere, the agents and target get spawned at random X, Y, and Z locations. The environments reset itself after every 50 frame-steps.
2	Big-Scale Environment	This environment is 100x100x20 open-type environment. This environment is close-to-real as it is vast and contains random sized buildings spawned at random locations. The agents and the target are also spawned at random locations. The environment resets itself if all agents crash for 256 times (this number is editable though) or each agent has taken more than 10240 action-steps.
3	Improved Big-Scale Environment	A 3D space covering a cubical volume of 1,000,000 <i>units</i> ³ , the length of each axis being 100 units, is assigned as the environment volume per simulation where 100 random sized obstacles ranging from 1 to 10 units of length, width, and height spawn at random positions

Table 4: Environment Designs

4.5 Hyperparameters

The following are the hyperparameters of the simulations:

Hyperparameter	Value
Number of Concurrent Simulation Runs	32
Number of Agents per Simulation (M)	16
Episode Length per Agent	1000 steps
Communication Radius (D_{com})	10 units
Number of Histogram Bins per Axis (K)	30
Number of Obstacle Sensors per Agent (J)	30
Sensor Range Limit (D_{sensor})	6 units
Safe Distance (D_{safe})	4 units

Table 5: Simulation Hyperparameters

Here, the PPO uses two networks called policy and critic network with 3 dense layers each having 128 neurons per layer. The learning hyperparameters are as follow:

Hyperparameter	Value
number of steps	30 million
time horizon	512 steps
batch size	1024 steps
sample buffer size	10240 steps
learning rate	0.0003
beta (penalty on policy update)	0.005
epsilon (clipping)	0.2
lambda (discount factor)	0.99
number of epochs	3
learning rate decay	linear

Table 6: Learning Hyperparameters (PPO)

4.6 Results

The learning curves obtained in the training for 30 million steps are as follows.

Figure 9: Mean Cumulative Reward

Figure 10: Mean Value Loss

Figure 11: Mean Entropy

To show the performance of our approach, visual observation of the swarm's behavior is necessary. So, in the following figures, visual observations of the swarm's versatile behavior are shown (a video playlist of these demos is available [here¹](#)). The agents are shown as green spheres, the red cube is the destination point and blue boxes represent the obstacles. A green-colored edge is formed between any two agents whenever they are in the communication region of each other. It is seen that the swarm is navigating properly by keeping a communication friendly organization among agents while avoiding any obstacles along the way.

¹ Video Playlist: <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLpWujOvrHLEdqV25JTsZWF-iaHKJjhUvt>

Figure 12: Result Visuals: Simple Environment

In the above figure, the agents are first navigating towards the destination point (Figure 12-a) because they have no information about locality yet due to their random start positions. Upon getting close to the destination, the agents sense each other and obstacles that are close to the destination point and organize in a way that they stay close to

each other and the destination point while keeping themselves away from the obstacles (Figure 12-b). Next, we moved the destination point to the opposite side (Figure 12-c to Figure 12-d) so that the swarm may experience the obstacles when moving towards the destination point. The agents managed to move through a space between the two obstacles to reach the destination point while staying connected (Figure 12-e to Figure 12-h).

In another test we observed the behavior of agents by increasing the problem complexity, the visuals are shown below.

Figure 13: Result Visuals: Complex Environment

In the above test, we first placed the destination point in an open space to let agents localize it (Figure 13-a), then the destination point was moved behind a set of obstacles which were covering the most area around it (Figure 13-b). Intelligent behavior can be seen in the trajectory of the swarm. The swarm body first elongated toward the destination point (Figure 13-c to Figure 13-d) which is a behavior we commonly see when a flock of birds moves. The elongation of the body of the swarm allows it to move through the less cross-sectional areas promising a safer journey. In the next two rows, a closeup view is shown in which the swarm is localizing the destination point while avoiding a horizontal obstacle on its way (Figure 13-e to Figure 13-f). Finally, the swarm localized the destination point, making a cup shape around it which is necessary to stay close to the destination point while avoiding the obstacles that are covering a whole side (Figure 13-g to Figure 13-h).

To test the robustness of the learned policy we created another interesting test. We placed a big obstacle between the destination point and the swarm. The big obstacle had only one hole from which only one agent could pass at a time. To ease out the inspection, here, the obstacle is set to be transparent. The following figure shows the swarm behavior over time. The agents were moving one-by-one in a row (Figure 14-a to Figure 14-d).

Figure 14: Result Visuals: Narrow Path Environment

The behavior seen is particularly interesting because such kinds of obstacles weren't present in the training environments.

In another interesting experiment we placed a moving destination point on a planner ground to measure the capability of the swarm to localize a constantly moving object, it is, therefore, a hard problem. We also improved visuals this time to give a better understanding of the swarm's behavior in real-world scenarios. The demonstrations are as follows (Figure 15-a to Figure 15-d):

Figure 15: Result Visuals: Moving Target Environment

Some other interesting cases can be seen in our video playlist on YouTube [here](#)¹.

¹ Video Playlist: <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLpWujOvrHLEdqV25JTsZWF-iaHKJjhUvt>

Chapter 5 : Conclusion and Future Directions

In this research, we presented an efficient way to train homogeneous agents of a swarm to navigate to a destination point in a 3D environment using a state-of-art DRL algorithm. We described a compact vector to present the state data to the neural network which generalizes the actions of the agents regardless of their locality in terms of neighboring agents. Moreover, to carefully craft a safe navigation behavior while keeping the swarm connected, a suitable reward function was formulated. The results indicate the generality of the approach by testing different conditions a swarm may encounter. We believe that this approach can be upscaled to be used in real-world artificial swarms.

Since this work assumes simplicities, a great amount of work can be done in the future including upscaled simulations, added environmental complexities like wind, gravity, and other environmental conditions. The use of memory enabled networks (RNNs) may improve path planning in maze-like environments.

A realization of this work in the future promises great applications. A particularly useful application of this model is search and rescue operations by using a swarm of hovering Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) like N-Copters (Tricopters, Quadcopters, etc.) where many sensors, communication devices, and powerful onboard computers are already available. Other use cases include distributed sensing, medical diagnosis and operations using nanobot swarms, and wireless networking, etc.

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